

Conference Abstract

When both prey (*Umbra krameri*) and predator (*Lutra lutra*) are strictly protected species

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Abstract

In our study (Suppl. material 1), we aimed to characterize the diet composition of the strictly protected Eurasian otter (*Lutra lutra*) by analyzing fish scales and pharyngeal teeth found in its feces (spraints). As a sampling site, we selected the Marótvölgyi Canal, one of Hungary's most important habitats for the European mudminnow (*Umbra krameri*). The samples collected originated from different years and seasons, providing a broad temporal overview. Due to the long-term fish monitoring program of the Balaton Limnological Research Institute, the fish fauna of the area is well-documented. However, further insights into the dietary preferences of local piscivorous animals, including otters, can be gained through the identification of fish scale remains in their spraints. In contrast to areas with large fish resources, the otter's diet in this canal includes a large proportion of small mammals, frogs, and water beetles. Preliminary results indicate that scales of the European mudminnow (*Umbra krameri*) were the most frequently occurring from fishes in the samples. The invasive and highly competitive Chinese sleeper (*Perccottus glenii*) was also present in the diet, albeit in lower quantities.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: poster [doi](#)

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